

Supporting Materials

Separation of Rosmarinic Acid from *Rosmarinus officinalis* L. by Ultrasonic-Assisted Extraction Using Biocompatible Ionic Liquid as Additive

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1. Optimization of the percentage of ethanol in water

Figure S1. The effect of ethanol concentration in the extractant on the extracted amount of rosmarinic acid (extraction time: 30 min, ultrasonic power: 150 W, extraction temperature: 30 °C, solvent to leaves ratio: 20 mL/g).

2. Parameter levels and results of response surface methodology.

Table S1. Parameter levels in the central composite design model for RSM.

Parameter	Level (code)		
	Low (-1)	Middle (0)	High (+1)
Solvent to leaves ratio (mL/g), X_1	10	15	20
Extraction time (min), X_2	20	40	60
Ultrasonic power (W), X_3	150	175	200
Extraction temperature (°C), X_4	20	30	40

Table S2. Extraction conditions and results used in CCD for response surface methodology.

Run	Solvent to leaves ratio (mL/g)	Time (min)	Ultrasonic power (W)	Temperature (°C)	Extracted amount (mg/g)	
					Actual value	Predicted value
1	10	20	200	20	18.73	18.69
2	10	20	150	20	18.77	18.75
3	10	20	200	40	18.78	18.77
4	10	20	150	40	18.88	18.83
5	20	20	200	20	18.97	18.93
6	20	20	150	20	19	18.98
7	20	20	200	40	19.08	19.12
8	20	20	150	40	19.12	19.17
9	10	60	150	20	19.2	19.20
10	10	60	200	20	19.21	19.15
11	20	60	200	20	19.22	19.31
12	10	60	200	40	19.31	19.37
13	15	20	175	30	19.31	19.44
14	20	60	150	20	19.37	19.36
15	10	60	150	40	19.41	19.43
16	15	40	175	20	19.56	19.74
17	15	40	200	30	19.56	19.59
18	20	60	150	40	19.62	19.69
19	15	40	150	30	19.62	19.64
20	20	60	200	40	19.64	19.64
21	10	40	175	30	19.69	19.85
22	15	40	175	30	19.95	19.99
23	15	40	175	30	19.97	19.99
24	15	40	175	30	19.99	19.99
25	15	40	175	30	20	19.99
26	15	60	175	30	20.01	19.93
27	15	40	175	30	20.02	19.99
28	15	40	175	30	20.07	19.99
29	15	40	175	40	20.08	19.95
30	20	40	175	30	20.2	20.09

3. Repetition of rosmarinic acid extraction under optimized conditions

Table S3. Repetition of rosmarinic acid extraction under the optimized conditions.

Entry	Amount of extracted rosmarinic acid (mg/g)	Average (mg/g)	RSD (%) (n=5)
1	21.16		
2	20.61		
3	20.52	20.88	1.40
4	21.04		
5	21.06		

Table S4. Comparison of the amount of extracted RA under the optimal conditions obtained in single factor optimization and RSM study.

Optimal conditions	Amount of extracted RA (mg/g)	
	Experimental value	Predicted value¹
Single factor optimization: 15 mL/g, 30 min, 175 W, 30 °C	19.30	19.78
RSM: 20 mL/g, 48 min, 175 W, 35 °C	20.88	20.16

¹Predicted value was calculated by Eq. (1) under the specific conditions.

4. Properties of macroporous resins

Table S5. Physical properties of the macroporous resins.

Resin	Surface area (m ² /g)	Average pore diameter (nm)	Density (g/mL)*	Material appearance
D101	500-550	9.0-10.0	0.23	
AB-8	480-520	13.0-14.0	0.36	
H103	1100-1200	8.6-9.5	0.58	
D152	540-580**	24**	0.70-0.75**	

*The densities were measured in our laboratory. **The values were from Ref. [1].

5. UPLC chromatogram

Figure S2. UPLC chromatograms of standard rosmarinic acid (A) and the extract obtained by [HEA][La]/ethanol solution (B).

6. Calibration curve

Figure S3. Calibration curve for quantification of rosmarinic acid by UPLC.

Reference

1. Long, Z.; Yang, C.; Zeng, G.; Peng, L.; Dai, C.; He, H. Catalytic oxidative desulfurization of dibenzothiophene using catalyst of tungsten supported on resin D152. *Fuel* **2014**, *130*, 19–24, doi:10.1016/j.fuel.2014.04.005.